

REVIEW OF KRIMIROGA IN AYURVEDA W.S.R. TO BALROGA**Vd. Renuka S. Jambhorkar¹ and Vd. Sneha Tiwari^{2*}**¹Professor, Balroga Shri K. R. Pandav Ayurved College, Nagpur.¹Associate Professor, Kayachikista Shri K. R. Pandav Ayurved College, Nagpur.***Corresponding Author: Vd. Sneha Tiwari**

Associate Professor, Kayachikista Shri K. R. Pandav Ayurved College, Nagpur.

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INTRODUCTION

Krimiroga is one of the most common diseases in the paediatric population. Krimi word has a wide meaning. All the organism which are dependent for food and shelter upon the human body can come under the title of Krimi. Our Acharyas described different classifications of Krimi. This classification includes all the microorganisms, bacteria, viruses, protozoa, and helminths, which totally depend upon the human body. Udara Krimis (Intestinal parasites) have been considered a major public health problem throughout the world.

Krimis produce a variety of symptoms. It is rather easy, when encountering symptoms related to Mahasrotas, to have stools investigated and have Krimi identified as a causative factor. An average child is doing poorly at school, harmful antibiotics are being administered unnecessarily to the child suffering from cough and fever, and the Krimis are unsuspected and undetected, which are responsible for exposing the victims to a large number of diseases by robbing them of their hard-earned nutrients, thus lowering their body defense. Hookworms suck 0.4 ml of blood per worm per day, thereby causing anemia and making them physically weak, remaining unhealthy throughout their life span. Acharya Charaka has beautifully described the threefold Chikitsa for Krimi Roga, viz. Apakarshana, Prakritivighata, and Nidan Parivarjana. Remarkably, in Apakarshana of Krimis, most vigorous Samshodhana, viz. Virechana, Vamana, Shirovirechana, and Asthapana, all of the four Karmas, have been advocated. But Samshodhana in children is not desirable, so this article reviews the Krimiroga and the possible treatment modality that can be incorporated in children.

CLASSIFICATION

According to the effect on the body

1. Sahaja Krimi: Those Krimi that do not cause any changes to human physiology are termed Sahaja Krimi. Some of them are found to be useful as Lactobacillus, etc. Such types of Krimi are cited in the buccal cavity of the mouth, alimentary canal, vaginal canal, etc.

2. Vaikarika Krimi: In general psychology of human beings that Krimi are harmful to the human body. Exactly this psyche is due to the Vaikarika type of Krimi. Means these are harmful Krimi.

According to Charka, they are divided into two types as Bahya and Abhyantara. According to the site of the body, Bahya Krimi (External worms). These worms originated externally, mainly occur in the hairy parts of the body. They may be considered responsible for the urticaria, furunculosis, and lymphadenitis. Example: Liksha & Yuka Abhyantara Krimi (Internal worms). This type of infection may occur due to the production of Ama, excessive consumption of a sweet and sour diet & virudhh ahaar. Example- Antrada, Udumbar.

According to the source of origin

- Malaja – originated from bahya mala
- Raktaja – originated from blood vessels (Dhamani)
- Kaphaja – originated from Amashaya (Stomach)
- Purishaja - originated from Pakvashaya (Large Intestine)

NIDAN PANCHAK

Samanya nidana – Samanya Nidana of Bahya Krimi: The external Krimis in the opinion of Charaka, Vagbhata, Madhavakara, and Bhavaprakasha are caused due to unhygienic and dirty habits (Mrijaverjanam). This is described as the cause of Malaja Krimis. Harita refers to its origin from sweat, dryness (of skin or body), and

worry (Yuka and Liksha). Samanya nidana of Abhyantara Krimi

Physical Factors

1. Avyayama

2. Diwaswapna

Diet articles 1. Godhuma 2. Masha 3. Vidala 4. Pishtanna 5. Prithuka 6. Bisa 7. Shaluka 8. Kasheruka 9. Patrashaka 10. Kshira 11. Dadhi 12. Guda 13. Sura 14. Sukta 15. Palala 16. Pishita 17. Anupamamsa 18. Ikshu

Taste & quality of diet

1. Madhura 2. Amla 3. Ruksha 4. Guru 5. Pichhila 6. Drava 7. Shitala 8. Tapodaka Diet habits Asatmya 2. Virudha 3. Malina 4. Adhyashana 5. Ajeerna RUPA like sweat)

Rupa of Bahya Krimi Kandu

2. Kotha

3. Pidaka

4. Ganda

Rupa of Abhyantara Krimi

1. Jwara 2. Vivarnata 3. Shoola 4. Hridroga 5. Bhrama 6. Bhaktadwesa 7. Atisara 8. Sadana 9. Vami 10. Jataragarjanam 11. Mandagni 12. Pipasa 13. Pitanetra

TREATMENT

Ayurvedic texts deal with the preventive as well as curative aspects to keep a human being healthy. In the 7th Chapter of Vimana Sthana, Charaka has given the three main procedures in the treatment of Krimi Roga.

1. Apakarshana

2. Prakriti Vighata

3. Nidana Parivarjana

Apakarshana(- Any process by which the unwanted elements are removed or extracted from the body is considered as Apakarshana. Apakarshana of Krimis includes the manual and instrumental removal of them, where it is applicable. Apakarshana of the Bahya Krimi and Abhyantara Krimi, which are migrated out to the external surface, should be done by the manual method. Apakarshana of Abhyantara Krimis, which resides in their usual habitat, should be done by the elimination method.

i. Vamana

ii. Virechana

iii. Shirovirechana

iv. Asthapan Basti

Prakriti Vighata

Bringing obstruction to the environment of origin and growth of Krimi is termed as Prakriti Vighata. It is derived from two words: 'Prakriti' means nature, and 'Vighata' means obstruction or to demolish. Prakriti Vighata is the process of counteraction of Krimi origination by Dravyas with Katu, Tikta, Kashaya, Kshara, and Ushna Guna. Other drugs having contrary properties to Purisha and Kapha are also used.

Nidana Parivarjana

Nidana Parivarjana means to eliminate the causative factors that help in producing, germinating, and the growth of Krimi. Hence, it is suggested to avoid the factors responsible for producing the Krimi.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Descriptions of Krimi in Samhita Granthas are in combined form. We can conclude all the microorganism parasites, helminths, bacteria, and viruses. Under the concept of Krimiroga, but protozoa and helminths are closer. Acharya Charak classified Krimi as Sahaja and Vaikarika means they are pathogenic and non-pathogenic krimi. Acharyas just mention non-pathogenic worms by their name as Sahaja. Under the Vaikarika Krimi, two subgroups are described as Bahya and Abhyantara Krimi. It means external Krimis can also create disease conditions. Acharyas further divided internal Krimis into three groups (1) Raktaja, (2) Purishaja, and (3) Shleshmaja according to their habitat and the media in which Krimis grow. Shleshmaja Krimi is one class of Krimi that grows on the Ama and lives in the stomach, small intestine, or upper part of gastro gastrointestinal tract. Purishaja Krimi is one class of Krimi which grows on fecal material and lives in Pakawasaya, the large intestine, or the lower part of gastro gastrointestinal tract. Raktaja Krimi lives in the blood and blood blood-forming organ (liver). Acharya Bhava Mishra described Raktaja Krimi as a causative factor of skin disease.

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